

Table S3*Status Publication and Index of Included Studies in the Systematic Review*

Author(s)	Journal	Year	Q1	Q2	Q3	Q4	Impact factor (JCR/SJR)
Affuso et al.	<i>The Journal of Educational Research</i>	2017			X		1.239
Affuso et al.	<i>European Journal of Psychology of Education</i>	2023		X			3.0
Andretta et al.	<i>Family Relations</i>	2017		X			1.727
Ben-Tov & Romi	<i>Education 3-13</i>	2019					0.355 (SJR)
Cross et al.	<i>Psychology in the Schools</i>	2019				X	1.134
Dong et al.	<i>Journal of Child and Family Studies</i>	2020		X			2.278
Grijalva-Quiñonez et al.	<i>Psicología Educativa. Revista de los Psicólogos de la Educación</i>	2020					-
Huang et al.	<i>International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health</i>	2021		X			4.614
Kristensen et al.	<i>Psychology in the Schools</i>	2023			X		2.0
Liu et al.	<i>Educational Psychology</i>	2019		X			1.586
Lv et al.	<i>Journal of Child and Family Studies</i>	2018		X			1.556
Rodríguez et al.	<i>Psicothema</i>	2017		X			1.516
Shi et al.	<i>Contemporary Educational Psychology</i>	2024	X				10.3
Sun et al.	<i>Learning and Individual Differences</i>	2020		X			3.139
Thomas et al.	<i>Learning Environments Research</i>	2019					1.219 (SJR)
Xu et al.	<i>Social Behavior and Personality</i>	2017				X	0.458
Yap & Baharudin	<i>Social Indicators Research</i>	2016	X				1.743

Note. All impact factors are sourced from the Journal Citation Report (JCR), except for Ben-Tov & Romi (2019) and Thomas et al. (2019), which are sourced from Scimago Journal Ranking (SJR).